

A Survey of Buddhist Sculptural Art from Coastal West Bengal

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Abstract

This paper highlights the extension, chronology and sculptural art of Buddhism from coastal West Bengal. This article also focuses on the classical foreign sources mainly the Chinese traveller accounts which reflect the continuation of the Buddhism in this area. The recent discoveries of sculptural art of Buddhist religion create a coherent picture of this area. A vast remote forest land which is geographically known as Sundarban area and central part of coastal West Bengal where considerable number of Buddhist image recovered has been discussed in this paper.

Key Words: Buddhism, Coastal West Bengal, Sundarban, Chinese account, Buddhist Sculpture.

Introduction

This paper has delineated a preliminary survey on Buddhist sculptural art from coastal west Bengal. Archaeological explorations and excavations during last decades in some early historic/early medieval sites in West Bengal have brought forth abundant and varied antiquities belonging to different eras. Among these rich assemblages of antiquities, some terracotta, stone, metal and bone objects earn particular consideration as these have got some association with Buddhism. The Bengal coast is stretch over widespread region lying roughly between East Medinipur in the west and Noakhali in the east. In the present paper our study area of 'coast' is limited to districts of East Medinipur (21°38'N to 22°30' N latitudes and 87°27'E' to 88°11'E longitude), North Twenty Four Parganas (22°11'6" N to 23°15'2" N latitudes and 88°20'E to 89°5' E longitude) and South Twenty Four Parganas (21°26'N to 21°38'N latitudes 87°57'E to 89°09' E longitude) in the present Indian state of West Bengal. The major archaeological sites where the Buddhist sculptural remains have been recovered are Tamruk, Panna, Tilda, Chandraketurgh, Barrackpur, Boral, Atagraha, Harinarayanpur, Baishata, Tilpi, Kankandighi, Nalgora, Sajenekhali, Bhangar-Dhara, Khalisadya, Maheshpur, Maipit and Patharpratima. This may be indicated that the unearthing of antiquities with Buddhist connection is nothing new in coastal Bengal as we have got some indications to prove that Buddhism had previously a stronghold in Bengal during the early centuries of the Christian era. The literary evidences show the missionary activities of Buddhism as recorded in *the Mahavamsa* (Sarkar, 1972: 74) and the travel accounts of eminent Chinese pilgrim scholars highlight the activities of the Buddhism in this region. The Buddhist *Jātakastories* mentioned the archaeological site Tamralipta (Sarkar, 1972: 74-75). The epigraphic records highlight the names of two donors in the railing of *stupa* in *Sanchi* (Bühler, 1984: 108 & 308), Madhya Pradesh, hailing from Pundravardhana (North Bengal) is important in this perspective. An epigraphical record from Nagarjunakonda (3rd Century A.D) (Vogel, 1983: P.23) comprised of a long list of well-known countries.

During the first decade of fifth century A.D the Chinese traveller Fa-hien visited India and he gave description of Tamralipti, a sea port of coastal Bengal. In his account he described a thriving condition of this Sea-port. According to Fa-hien that time about twenty-four *Sanghārāmas* were present in this area. Fa-hien dwelt for two years in this area for the purpose of studying Buddhism. He stayed in one of these *Sanghārāms* copied the sacred book and portrayed images (Beal, 1966: Ixxi). This ancient sea port Tamralipta now identified as modern Tamluk, is located in east Medinipur district of West Bengal. Hiuen Tsang, another Buddhist traveller came in India during the seventh century A.D and visited this area. In this period time about ten *Sanghārāms* and fifty temples existed in the coastal land. According to Hiuen Tsang, thousands of priests and several sectaries lived in this area. In his account he mentioned about a *stūpa* in this area which was built by Aśoka, situated by the side of the city (Beal, 1966: 200-201).

According to I-tsing (A.D. 671) another Chinese traveller described a comprehensive picture of Buddhism in Tamralipti in his account. During his journey, he met another Chinese person and *mahayan Pandit* Ta-Cheng-teng. I-tsing stayed in Tamralipti for one year and he studied Brahmi-language (Sanskrit) and practiced the science of the words (grammar, *sabdatvidya*) (Takakusu, 1896: XXXiii). In this period he described monastic organisation in this area. According to him “I also observed that every morning the managing priest (of that monastery) examined water on the side of a well; that if there was no insect in it, that water was used, and if there was a life in it, it was filtered, that whenever anything, even a stalk of vegetable, was given (to the priests) by others persons, they made use it through the assent of the assembly; that no principal office was appointed in that monastery; that when any business happened, it was settled by the assembly; and that, if any priest decided anything by himself alone, or treated the priest decided anything himself alone, or treated the priests favourably or unfavourably at his own pleasure, without regarding the will of the assembly, he was expelled (from the monastery) being called a *Kulapati* (i.e. he behaved like householder)” (Takakusu, 1896: 62-63). According to I-tsing “...on the four *upavasatha*-days of every month a great multitude of priests, all having assembled there late in the after moon from several monasteries, listened to reading of the monastic rites, which they obeyed and carried out with increasing reverence (Takakusu, 1896: 63)”.

During this time there was Bhikshu named A-ra-hu (not ‘shi’) la Mitra (Rahula Mitra) in that monastery. He is same person Rahulaka, whose verses are mentioned in the *Subhāsītāvali* of Vallabhadeva. According to I-tsing “He was then about thirty years old; his conducted was very excellent and his fame was exceedingly great. Every day he read over the *Rantnakūtasūtra*. Which contains 700 verses. He was not only versed in the three collections of the scriptures, but also thoroughly conversant with secular literature on the four sciences. He was honoured as the head of the priests in the eastern districts of India” (Takakusu, 1896: 63-64).

I-tsing mentioned about teaching, learning and ritual rites of a monastery in Tamralipti whose name was Bha-ra-ha (Barahat or Varāha) (Takakusu, 1896: 65).

M.M. Haraprasad Sastri says that about 1000 years ago, there were numerous Buddhist *viharas* in the tract now known as Coastal Bengal, where Buddhist monks wrote their books and preached their faith. He exemplified two important places Hatiagarh and Balanda where there were *Vihāras* and the monks studied the *prajñāpāramitā* (Chaudhuri *et al*, 2001: 244). Nalini Nath Dasgupta (Dasgupta, 1355 (BS): 217) and Devaprasad Ghosh (Ghosh, 1968: 48 &

50) accepted the view of Pandit Sastri regarding the existence of *Vihāra* at Balanda. Pandit Sastri refers to a manuscript of *Aṣṭasahasrikāprajñāpāramitā* preserved in the Royal library of Nepal (Now Bir Library) as the ground of his argument.

Khasaparna Lokānth was an important deity at Khāḍi (South Twenty Four parganas). In the *Sādhanamālā* there is a story regarding the installation of this image. A pious merchant named Śubhāṅkara was on the commercial expedition to Potalok a port of Western India. During this voyage he passed a night at Khasaparna, a village at Khāḍī-mandala. Avalokiteśvara appeared to him in his dream and asked him not to proceed further and to establish the deity according to the rule of the *Vairocanatantra*. Through this he would attain prosperity and merit. The merchant accordingly installed the image of Avalokiteśvara (Sen, 1985:P.162).

This area as a centre of Buddhism was first mentioned in *Dākrnava Tantra* where it mentioned about *pithas* (*Khadi*) like *Radha*, *Dhikkara*, *Vangala* and *Harikela* (Sastri, 1917:P.92). The Rakshaskalicopper plate inscription of *Madanapaladeva* mentioned a Buddhist *Vihāra* which was situated outside of the village of *Vahamitā* and was called *Ratnatraya Mahāvihāra*. Several Buddhist images in different periods highlight this region as one of the important Buddhist centres during early historic and early medieval periods (Sen & Ghosh, 1934:321-33; Ghosal, 1947-8:119—24; Sircar, 1953-4:42-46).

DHYANI BUDDHA AKSOBHYA

The earliest Buddhists considered the timeless existence of five *Skandhas* or cosmic elements—*rupa* (form), *Vedāna* (sensation), *Samjna* (name), *Samsakara* (conformation) and *Vijnana* (Consciousness). These components are consecrated in the *Vajrayana* as the five Dhyani Buddhas, originating from the highest mortal Vajradhara, often recognized with *Sunya* and *Adi Buddha*. The five Dhyani Buddhas are Amitabha, Aksobhya, Vairocana, Amoghasiddhi and Ratnasambhava. They are the progenitor of the five families of deities (*Kulas*) representing the entire Buddhist family. Each Dhyani Buddha has a *Sakti*, a *Bodhisattva*, a number of secretions, a male and female, and an identification emblem. They are seated on a full-blown lotus and in *dhyansana*. The hands resting on the lap is sometimes pouring, but in most of the cases it bears a bowl. The head bears thick clustering curling of hair. The half-closed eyes are another feature of the images. The proper narratives of the Dhyani Buddha are mentioned in *Adayavajrasamgraha*. Their icons are broadly illustrated in miniature forms on the head of their emanations. They are sculpted on the four side of the *Stupas*—Amitabha facing the west, Aksobhya the east, Amoghasiddhi the north and Ratnasambhava the south. Vairocana's place is in the sanctum of the *Stupas* and for this reason he is not visualised on its body. Individual iconographic form of the *Dhyani Buddha* is not exceptional but it is very familiar in Nepal and Tibet.

An image of Dhyani Buddha Aksobhya has been found from Kankandighi, now preserved in a private collection. The god seated on a full blossom lotus in *dhyāna* posture. The important features of this image are his half-closed eyes, divine smile and well built body. His right hand shows *bhumisparsha-mudrā* and left hand holds *Śakti* his consort Mamaki. The well decorated halo is another feature of this image. The lower portion of his body is covered by dhoti like garments and the upper portion shows a folded *sanghati*, the ends of which is placed on the left Shoulder. On the basis of stylistic consideration this image can be dated c. 7th century A.D.

BODHISATTVA

PLATE-I

A head of *Bodhisattva* datable to c. 6th century A.D has been found from Atghara (PLATE-I). It is now preserved in a private collection. The half-closed eyes, sharp nose and a divine smile are notable features of this terracotta specimen.

Another head of *Bodhisattva* has been recovered from Tamluk area can be dated to c.5th century A.D. It is now preserved in Archaeological Survey of India Museum at Tamluk. The oval face of the figure with flaccid eyelids, sensuous lips, divine smile and the mind fascinated within expresses an appearance of spirituality. The accurate curls of the hair turning to the sight another important feature of the image(PLATE II). Similar type of *Bodhisattva* image recovered from Tamluk area can be dated to c.5th century A.D now preserved in Archaeological Survey of India Museum at Tamluk.

PLATE- II

BUDDHA IMAGE

The numerous Buddha images have been recovered from all the parts of India. The eastern Indian Buddhism played a crucial role in India. The coastal Bengal is ntan exception in this regard. A considerable number of Buddha images has been recovered from this remote forest land which reflects the well-founded Buddhist establishment in this region. Large number of Buddha images of terracotta, stone, metal and bronze have been discovered in this area. The majority of images are in seating posture. Two standing images of Buddha have also been recovered from this area.

The earliest Buddha image, so far recovered in coastal Bengal, has been collected from Khana-MihirerDhipi, at Berachapa in the vicinity of Chandraketurarh. The image belongs to second century A.D. According to S.K Saraswati (Saraswati,1962:12): "The head and bust of Buddha-Bodhisattva from Chandraketurarh have all the characteristic traits of the colossal Kūshan Buddha-Bodhisattva images found in such sites as Saranath,

Sahet-Mahet, Kousambi, Mathuraetc.and though in miniature form, has the same stolid dignity in its physical form and bearing. Both hands are broken away, the right completely. The left, of which the upper portion now remains, seems from its positions, to have been held

to waist. A drapery covers the left shoulder and the upper torso, the folds being indicated by prominent ridges on the left upper arm. Here we find a sturdy bust with a heavy neck, all distinctive of the physical type of Kushan Buddha-Bodhisattva images. On the upper torso the drapery is to a certain extent, diaphanously treated revealing the modelling underneath. An attempt towards a thin and transparent treatment of the drapery may assign the fragment to a period not earlier than the second century A.D.”

PLATE-III

A low relief sculpture of Buddha is depicted on a brick in meditation posture have been recovered from Chandraketurgh(PLATE III), now preserved in Dr.G.S De’s private collection. This image of Buddha seated on a throne in *mahārājālīlāsana* posture. Three lions are depicted below the throne. His right hand rests on thigh and left hand is *inabhaya-mudrā*. The halo has been depicted behind his head. Two flying *vidyādhara*s are found on both sides of the halos. Two male attendants are there on both sides of the Buddha. They hold fly whisk. The important features of this image are divine smile, bare face, ameliorated chest and magnanimous shoulder. This image of Buddha closely resembles with Katra image of Buddha from Mathura. On the basis of stylistic consideration this image can be dated 2nd/3rd century A.D.

PLATE IV

A terracotta image of Buddha has been recovered from Haroa, a close vicinity of Chandraketurgh, now preserved in DilipMaiti’s private collection highlights Buddha engaged in preaching his first sermon (*dharmacakrapravartanmudrā*). The highly decorated halo with flying *Vidhyādaras* on the upper corner and the *makara* and similar figures on the sides, a reminiscent of Gupta images in stone from Saranath. The face though mutilated shows his eyes absorbed within. Elongated earlobes, hair tied in a top knot have been magnificently delineated by the artist. The Buddha wears *Sanghati* covering both the shoulders. Below the Buddha’s seat a wheel is shown diagonally, indicating the Deer park at Sarnath where Buddha delivered the first Sermon. This specimen of art can be dated 7th century A.D. Another same type of image has been recovered from same area now preserved in Khas Balanda Pratna Gabeshnakendra (PLATE IV).

Another image of Buddha has been recovered from Haroa, now preserved in DilipMaiti’s private collection. In this image, Buddha is seated in *Yogasana* posture on a raised seat. The god is bare-bodied and wearing a lion-cloth, the fold

of which sling in the centre and rest on the seat. His right hand is raised to his chest in the gesticulation of assertion and left hand is placed on his left thigh. The round face, open-eyed expression and callous built body with shorter neck deserve attention. The curls of the hair have been delivered somewhat imprecisely as if twisted. The cranial bump over the head is very distinct. Thus, the diminutive coiled hair, the obtrude *Usnisha* and the extended earlobes symbolize the extraordinary virtues (*mahapurusalaksmana*). The whole figure is set off adjacent to a semi-circular nimbus having notched markings at the both limits and *astupika* in the centre of the arch on the top. The image can be dated c.8th /9th century A.D.

A *dhyānamurti* of Buddha has been found from Kankandighi, now preserved in Chattrabhog-Khari sangrahasala and is dated to c.7th c A.D. Buddha is seated on a two-tiered pedestal. His two hands are placed on his lap. His curling hair, elongated ear, closed eyes, and *Urna* on his forehead are important features of this image.

PLATE- V

A votive *Stupa* from Baishata(PLATE V) shows four major incidents of Buddha's life. Four images of the Buddha are carved in the four different niches of the *stupa* in *vitarkamudra*, *dharmachakrapravartanamudra*, *bhumisparshamudra*, and *padmāsana* with a mango in his hand. This art object is dated between the last part of the 7th century and first half of the 8th century AD. It is now preserved in Pratnatattvik Kalidas Dutta Sangrahasala (Jaynagar)

Another terracotta plaque of Buddha has been recovered from Panna, now preserved in Ashutosh Museum of Indian Art University of Calcutta. God is seated on *padmasana* on one tier pedestal. He possesses *dharmachakrapravartanamudra*. The early guptabrahmi creed is engraved on the stella (*Indian Archaeology 1957-58 A Review P.72 Pate LXXXVII*).

An image of Vajrasana Buddha c. twelfth century A.D. has been recovered from Barrackpore (*Indian Archaeology 1957-58 A Review P.72 Plate XCI A*) area of North Twenty-Four Parganas district. The god is seated on a *visvapadma*. His left hand is situated on his lap and right hand shows *bhumisparshamudra*. Five, dhyani Buddha engraved on the stella. Two female companions are standing on both sides of the god.

PLATE VI

PLATE VII

Another image of Buddha in meditation has been found from Kankandighi. It shows the Lord seated on *dhyāna* posture inside a temple. Some elongated *stupikā* encircled this image (c. 8th century A.D) (PLATE VI). This image is situated in Sundarbanpratna-GabeshanaKendra, Kasinagar.

A magnificent sealing has been recovered from Kankandighi, now preserved in Pratnatattvik Kalidas Dutta Sangrahasala (Jaynagar). Lord Buddha is seated in *bhumisparsamudra* under a pillared decked arch with leaves. This type of sealing closely resembles clay lumps found from *Sāñchi* with similar motifs dated to c. 7th c. A.D. (PLATE VII)

The image from Birinchibari (Mukhopadhyay, 2005:2) shows the god seated on a full blossomed lotus, placed on a rectangular pedestal. The right hand shows *vitarkamudra* and left hand rests on lap. The god wears a *dhoti* type garment in the lower part of the body and the upper portion is covered with a folded *sangati*, the end of which runs down from the front of the left arm. This image has curling hair, half-closed eyes and a halo in the back of the head consisting of lotuses. This image of the *Buddha* closely resembles some aspects of the *Buddha* of the Mathura School of sculptures. This image can be dated to c. 6th c AD.

PLATE VIII

PLATE-IX

Another image of *Buddha* which is made of black basalt was recovered from Kankandighi. *Buddha* is here seated on a throne. He is displaying *dharmachakrapravartanamudra*. He wears a long tight fitting garment. He wears a *mukuta*, *kanthahara* and *karnakundala*. This image is dated to c. 7th- 8th century A.D. and preserved in Sundarbanpratna-GabeshanaKendra, Kasinagar (PLATE VIII).

An image of *Buddha*, found from Sajnekhali (preserved in a local temple) shows the god seated on a two-tiered pedestal, in *dhyāna* posture. His two hands are in *dharmachakramudra*. The curling hairs are carved very distinctly. Two elongated votive stupas are placed on both sides of the upper part of the stela. This image is dated to c. 10th c AD. (PLATE IX)

Another image of *Buddha* was found from Atghara (Satyajug 18th June 1980 p.5). It shows the Lord seated in *dhyāna* posture. His left hand is in *bhumisparshamūdra*. But the important thing is that its pedestal shows an 11th –12th century proto-Bengali inscription (*Ratnatraya-Buddhavihara-Vikshu-Sanghasa*). This specimen displays some sort of Tibetan or Burmese art idioms in its physiognomical representation.

A broken image of *Buddha* from Kankandighi, which is now preserved in Dutta's house shows the god seated on a *viśvapadma*, showing *dhāyanamūdra*. The central figure is encircled by many small images of *Buddha*. This specimen is dated to c. 10th c. AD.

A headless *pralambapadi* image of *Buddha* has been found from Salika – Maheshpur and can be dated to c. 8th/9th century A.D. *Buddha* is here seated on a throne. He is displaying *dharmachakrapravartanamūdra*. He wears a long tight-fitting garment. This image now preserved in a local temple.

An image of *Buddha* is recovered from Krishnachandrapur, now preserved in a private museum. The image is seated on a one tiered pedestal in padmasana posture. The right hand of the god rests on lap and left hand possesses *abhyay- mudra*. A round shaped halo is situated back of the head. The oval shaped face, sharp nose, half closed eyes, curling hair and long ears are the physiognomical feature of the image. The lower portion of his body is covered by a *dhoti* like garment and the upper portion shows a folded *shangati* the ends of which is placed on the left shoulder. Another similar type of image has been recovered from Krishnachandrapur preserved in a private collection. These images can be dated 7th century A.D., on the stylistic consideration.

A number of small votive images of *Buddha* have been recovered from adjacent area of Jatar Deul. The god is seated on arch like architectural motif in *dhyanamudra*. The right hand shows *bhumisparshamudrā* and the left hand rests on the lap. These specimens display some sort of Tibetan art idioms in its physiognomical representation. On the basis of stylistic consideration these images can be c. 11th century A.D.

Six images of Buddha in *bhumispasha-mudra* posture have been recovered from adjacent area of Jatar Deul⁴⁰, now preserved in a private museum in Sundarban. The first image shows the god seated on a two-tier pedestal in dhyana posture under an arch type motif. This image is made by black basalt. His left hand shows *bhumisparsha-mudra* and right hand rest on lap. The round face, long ears, half-closed eyes, carling hairs, thick lips, snub-nose are the physical feature of the image. A prominent Urna is visible on his forehead. This art specimen closely resemble with Burmese art idion, can be dated 9th /10th century A.D. The second specimen of art which is recovered from same area highlights the god seated on a lotus based one tier pedestal. The lower portion of his body is covered by a *dhoti* like garment and the upper portion shows a folded *shangati* the ends of which is placed on the left shoulder. The closed eyes, tranquil face, blooming smile, and divine physiognomical form are the important character of this image. The physical anatomy of the third and fourth specimens of the image of Buddha of this group bears close similar with second art idioms. These specimens of art can be date 9th /10th century A.D. Two specimens of the images of Buddha have been recovered from same vicinity highlights the god seated on lotus based one tier pedestal. The lower portion of his body is covered by a *dhoti* like garment and the upper portion shows a folded *shangati* the ends of which is placed on the left shoulder. The left hand of the god shows *bhumisparsha-mudra* and right one rests on lap. The half closed eyes, tranquil oval shaped face, elongated ears, carling hairs with knot, prominent eyebrows and smiley lips are the basic features of the images. On the basis of stylistic consideration these art specimens go to 9th /10th century A.D.

An excellent basalt stone image of Buddha discovered from Raidighi now preserved in local police station is a noteworthy addition to the Buddhist sculptural repertoire of Bengal. Standing on a lotus placed on a decorated *pancharatha* pedestal, the Master is presented in strict frontality or *Samapadaasthanaka* posture. His transparent monastic robe covers the broad shoulders and coming down much below the knee. Both the fore arms of the image are broken from the elbows. But the position of the upper arms it appear that the right hand was originally raised in *abhyay-mudra*, while the left one was slightly lowered balancing the right one. The image is standing under a magnificent architectural motif. Two flying *Vidhyadhara* bears garland is situated both side Buddha. A stupa motif is situated upper part of the architectural motif. The round face, closed eyes, bare legs, thick lips, sharp nose, coiled hair with knot are the basic feature of the images. This image can be dated 11th century A.D. (PLATE X)

PLATE-X

PLATE-XI

PHOTO COURTESY –DIRECTORATE
OF ARCHAEOLOGY AND MUSEUM
GOVERNMENT OF WEST BENGAL

One of the significant collections of the Asutosh Museum of Indian Art University of Calcutta is a black stone sculpture depicts *Mahaparinirvana* seen of *Buddha* found from Khalisady. This piece of sculpture is important both from the iconographic and artistic point of view. The row of five *Dhyānī Buddhas* on the top, *Indra* or *Sakra* in regal costume holding a parasol beside the rising *stupa* in the background, the kneeling figure of *Brahma* and with *Jatamukuta*, the feet of the dying *Buddha* with both hands, are unusual the traditional pair of *sāla* trees of Kusinagara between which the couch of the *Buddha* is usually placed, the mourning monks including the mediating figure of *Subhadra*, the last disciple of the departed master seated under the couch according to the idiom of the Eastern School are conspicuous by their absence.

An image of Buddha has been recovered from Deganga (North Twenty FourParaganas), now preserved in Directorate of Archaeological Museum Govt. of West Bengal. The god seated on a *visvapadma* placed on a three-tiered pedestal. His right hand possesses *bhumisparshamudra* and left hand rest on lap. The Dhyani Buddhas is situated top of the stela. Two female attending figure is situated both side of the god. Two devotees are kneeling below the pedestal. This image can be dated c. 11th /12th century A.D.(PLATE XI)

An image of Buddha has been recovered from North Twenty Four Parganas now preserved in Directorate of Archaeology and Museum Govt. of west Bengal. The god seated on a *visva-padma* in *dhyana* posture. Buddha is in the *bhumisparsa-mudra* with his right palm touching the pericarp of the *visva-padma*. The left palm is placed on the soles of the feet. The rigid pose, the sculpt of the upper body and the outline of the arms close influence with late Gupta example of art. The surrounding stela closely resemble with the Buddha from Salban Vihara, Mainamaticomilla. This image can be dated early seventh century A.D on the stylistic consideration.

PLATE-XII

A metal image of Buddha has been recovered from Chandraketurah (PLATE XII) now preserved in Dr. Gourisanakar De private collection. Buddha, seated on an oval shaped full blossomed lotus pedestal. He is in *dhyanamudra* posture. A decorated round shaped halo has been situated behind this image. The robust body, royal physiognomical attributes, sullen face and conventional garb reflects an ascetic feature of this image. The reverse of the image is very magnificent for its artistic skillness. The *Garuda* hold a wheel by his hand. *Garuda* is flapping his both wings. The vigorous motion this *Garuda* image creates an astonishing manifestation of this art specimen. A small corroded inscription of late Gupta *brahmi* has been situated back of the

image. On the basis of epigraphical records this image can be dated 7th century A.D.

Another image of Buddha has been recovered from Chandraketurah area, now preserved in Dr. Gourisanakar De private collection. The god seated on lotus like oval shaped pedestal. He is in *dhyana* posture. His right hand in *Vyakhana-mudra* and left hand lies on the soles of feet. A round shaped halo is situated back of the god. The closed eyes, celestial smile and divine physiognomical feature imperative attributions of this image. The lower portion of his body is covered by dhoti like garments and the upper portion shows a folded *Sangati* the ends of which is placed on the left Shoulder. On the basis of the Stylistic ground this image can be date 9th /10th century A.D.

An image of Buddha has been found from Maipit area of Sundarban, now preserved in a private collection. The God seated on an oval shaped pedestal in *dhyana* posture. His right hand shows *bhumisparsha-mudra* and left hand lies on the soles of feet. His elongated ears, half closed eyes, curling hair and well-arranged monastic drapery reflects this image closely resemble with Nalanda Buddha images. A prominent *urna* has been situated forehead of the Buddha. This image can be dated 10th century A.D on stylistic consideration.

A bronze image of headless Buddha has been recovered from Patpukur, in Baishata area and it can be dated to c.10th century A.D. The god is seated in *vajraparjankasana* posture and his two hands possess *dharmachakrapravartan-mudra*. This image is now preserved inin Directorate of Archaeology and Museum Govt. of west Bengal

PLATE-XIII

PHOTO COURTESY –DIRECTORATE
OF ARCHAEOLOGY AND MUSEUM
GOVERNMENT OF WEST BENGAL

A metal *Buddha*, standing on a three tiered rectangular pedestal, in *sthanaka* posture has been found from Kankandighi area and preserved in the Directorate of Archaeology and Museum Government of West Bengal. The right hand of *Buddha* shows *abhayamudra* and holds the hem of the robe. The *Buddha* wears a folded *Shangati* which covers both the arms and shoulders. He is accompanied by a couple of miniature images of Boddhisattvas having same hand position as in the evident form the central figure. This image is dated to c.10th century A.D(PLATE-XIII).

Another bronze image of *Buddha* has been found from Patharpratima (c.10th century A.D). It can be compared with the Jhewari group of bronzes on the basis of stylistic consideration. In this image Buddha is seated on a rectangular pedestal in *dhyana* posture. His right hand shows *bhumisparsa-mudra* and left hand rests on his lap. The lower portion of his body is covered by a *dhoti* like garment and the upper portion shows a folded *shangati* the ends of which is placed on the left shoulder. This image now preserved in private collection.

Another metal image of Buddha has been recovered from Bhangar (c.11th century A.D). This image is seated on a two-tiered lotus like rectangular pedestal in *dhyanasana* posture. His right hand shows *abhaya-mudra* and the left hand rests on the lap. The lower portion of his body is covered by a *dhoti* like garment and the upper portion shows a folded *shangati* the end of which is placed on the left shoulder. It is now preserved in local police station.

A metal image of Buddha has been recovered from Maipit area and it can be dated 11th century A.D. This image now worshiped in a local villager's house. The Buddha seated on a rectangular pedestal in *dhyana* posture. His right hand shows *bhumisparsa-mudra* and left hand rests on lap. *Anuran* has been situated on his forehead.

PLATE-XIV

A magnificent image of Buddha has been recovered from Kankandighi,(Plate-XIV) now preserved in the local museum of sundarban. His right hand rests on lap and left possesses *abhaya-mudra* posture. He is seated on an oval shaped pedestal. He wears royal type of garment on his body. His prominent eyebrows, elongated ears, cylinder tapering eyes, sharp nose and thick lips. The important feature of the image is the life of Buddha depicting on the back side of the pedestal. This image can be dated 11th century A.D.

An image of Buddha has been recovered from Maipit, now preserved in a private collection. The god is seated on a three-tier pedestal. His right hand possesses *abhaya-mudra* and left hand shows *varada-mudra*. He wears *dhoti* and *sangati* like garments. His half-closed eyes, elongated ears, sharp nose, prominent eyebrows, thick lips and carling hair with top knot important features of the images. The pedestal of the image is very interesting. It is divided into two parts. The below parts engraved lotus petals. The second row divided into three rows. The second row depicted two elephants both side and an auspicious symbol is situated middle register of the pedestal. This image can be dated 10th /11th century A.D.

Another image of Buddha has been recovered from Chandanpiri, a core forest area Sundarban. The right hand of the god possesses *Varada-mudra* and and left hand shows rest on lap. The lord Buddha seated on lotus based oval shaped pedestal. The God wears *Sangati* and *dhoti* like garments. His half closed eyes, elongated ears, sharp nose, prominent eyebrows, thick lips and carling hair with top knot important features of the images. This image is belongs to 10th century A.D.

PLATE-XV

Few years ago an image of Buddha an excellent piece of wood carving, was discovered from kankandighi. This image of the Lord in meditation is seated crossed-legged in *Padmasana* on a *Visvapadma*. His round face, half closed eyes, spiral coils of hair rolling down to the ears and the top knot (*Ushinisha*) are all curved out meticulously. The left hand of the image shows *abhaya-mudra* and the right one rests on the lap exhibiting *vitarka*. The lower portion of the body is covered by a *dhoti* and the left part of the upper portion shows a folded *shangati*, the end of which runs down in front of the left arm. Stylistically, this image of Buddha has close resembles with some of the similar images from Nepal and may be dated c.9th -10th century A.D (PLATE XV). This image now preserved in Sundarban Pratna-Gabeshana Kendra Kasinagar.

BUDDHIST DEITIES

A number of Buddhist deities have been noticed in this area. The most important image in this regard is a *Manjusri* image which has been found from Bhangor and is now preserved in the Asutosh Museum of Indian Art, University of Calcutta. The image is in *sthānaka* posture on a pedestal. He wears different types of ornaments. His left hand holds an *utpala* and right hand exhibits *varadamūdrā*. Two attendants are standing on both sides of the Lord. Five *dhyānī Buddhas* are visible around his head. According to the description of *Sādhanamālā* the image is an example *Siddhaikavīra Manjusri* of the *Manjusri* group. This image is dated to c. 11th c. A.D.

An eight handed, three headed *Mārichī* have been found from Kankandighi and now preserved in Chatrabhog-khari Museum. She wears *Karandamukuta* on her heads. She wears a sari like garment and stands in *ālīdha* posture. The weapons of the deity are not very

distinct. Few of them can be identified as the *dhanusha*, *bāna*, *ankuśa* and *aśakapuspa*. The image stands under a *chityagriha*. The *pādapītha* is like a *ratha*. This *ratha* divided some rooms. The chambers depict some small animals carrying the chariot. The animals are most probably boars. The charioteer is seated in the middle of the chariot. This image can be dated to c. 10th century A.D

PLATE- XVI

Some images of *Tārā*, another important Buddhist goddess, were found from this region. Such images have been found from Boral, Atghara, Kankandighi. The image from Boral which is dated to 11-12th c. A.D is now in the *Tripurasundari* temple. In this image the *Devī* is standing in *Pratyālidha* posture on pedestal. She wears a long *mala*, which is formed by human skulls. Another *Tārā* image of c. 11th c. A.D was found from Kankandighi and is now preserved in the State Archaeology Museum, Calcutta. The *Devī* holds an *utpala* stalk in the right hand, while a *stupikā* is carved on the stella⁶⁰. Another image of *Tārā* found from Haroya (PLATE XV) is now preserved in a local museum of Baruipur and is dated to c. 10th - 11th c. AD. Here the *Devī* is seated on a lotus pedestal. Her left hand holds a *padma* and right hand rests on her lap. She wears a *karandamukta* on her head and she is decked by different types of ornaments⁶¹.

PLATE-XVII

A magnificent image of *Padmapani* recovered from Kankandighi (PLATE-XVII) has close affinity with Nepalese sculpture preserved in Museum of Fine Arts, Boston. The God stands on *samapadasthanaka* posture on a two-tiered lotus pedestal. His left hand holds a lotus stalk and right hand possess *Varadamudra*. The god is bejewelled by several types of ornaments. On the stylistic grounds this image can be dated late Gupta or pre-Pala. This image is situated in Dr. Tulsicharan Bhattacharya Smriti Sangrahasala (South Vishnupur).

Another *Bodhisattva* image has been recovered from Ghosherchak, Baishata, now preserved in Dr Ramtaran Chakraborti Archaeological Heritage Museum. The God seated on an oval shaped pedestal in *lalitasana* posture. His left hand shows *abhyaya-mudra* and right hand holds a jar with *Kalpavrksa*. A

prominent *urna* has been situated on his forehead. His elongated ears, half closed eyes, charming face, curling hair and well arranged monastic drapery reflects this image closely resemble with Nepalese art. Some wheel symbol has been situated on his back. This image

identified as *Bodhisattva Ksitigarbha* on the basis of *Sadhanamala*. On the basis of the stylistic consideration this image can be dated first half of the 8th century A.D.

Aksayamati another form of *Bodhisattva* has been recovered from Maipitarea and it can be dated c.11th century A.D. The God seated on an oval shaped pedestal. According to *Nispannayayogabali* his two hands hold the bowl containing the nectar of knowledge. This specimen of art closely resembles with Tibetan school of art. Another similar type of *Bodhisattva Akyasamati* image has been recovered from Maipit area and it can be dated c.11th century A.D. The god seated on an oval shaped pedestal. He is in *lilasana* posture. According to *Nispannayayogabali* his two hands hold the bowl containing the nectar of knowledge. The important features of this image are round shaped, half closed eyes, well arranged dress and divine smile. This image now preserved in Dr. Tulsicharan Bhattacharya Smriti Sangrahasala (South Vishnupur).

Sadaksari Lokesvara is regarded as another form of *Bodhisattva Avalokitesvara* according to *Sadhanamala*. A metal image *Sadaksari Lokesvara* from Kankandighi is dated to c.9th /10th century A.D. The image shows the divinity on a four tiered pedestal on *vajnkasanraparyaa* posture. His front hands are in *anjali* mudra and the back right hand holds a rosary and the back left hand is broken. He wears *akarandamukuta* and there are different types of ornaments on his body. This image now preserved in Dr. Tulsicharan Bhattacharya Smriti Sangrahasala (South Vishnupur).

The *Jambhala* is regarded as an emanation of *Aksobhya* as well as that of *Ratnasambhava*. He is regarded as the God of wealth. A metal image of *Jambhala* (c.9th century A.D) found from Kankandighi, now preserved in Bhuvan Museum, shows the god seated on two-tiered oval shaped pedestal in *ardhaparyankasanaposture*. The upper part of the body of the divinity is bare. His head is decorated by a trident in the middle of which a *Bodhisattva* image is visible. *Jambhala* wears different type of ornament and his right hand holds a purse and left hand holds a mongoose vomiting jewel.

JHAM

PLATE-XVIII

The goddess *Nairatma* emanating the dhyani Buddha *Akshobhya* is well delineated in a bronze image found from *Katandighi*. The goddess is dancing on a round three decked lotus pedestal in *ardhaparyanka* posture. She is standing on corpse. Her right hand holds *Vajrakarti* and left hand bears *Kapāla*. She is adorned with five ornaments such as *kanthika*, *rucaka*, *ratna*, *mekhala* and *sutra* and according to *sadhanamala* these are five auspicious ornaments of the goddess. The *dhyānī* Buddha *Akshabhay* is visible in her crown. This image is dated to c.9th -10th century A.D.(PLATE-XVIII)

lalitāsana posture. Her right hand is broken and her left hand holds a fruit. She does not wear any ornament except a *karanda-mukuta* which is seen on her head. It is now preserved in Directorate of Archaeology and Museum Government of West Bengal.

A metal Buddhist image of *Tārāhas* been recovered from *Kankandighi* and is dated to c. 8th century A.D on the basis of stylistic considerations. In this image *Tara* is seated on the three tiered lotus pedestal in

PLATE-XIX

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OF ARCHAEOLOGY AND MUSEUM
GOVERNMENT OF WEST BENGAL

A Buddhist tantric goddess has been recovered from *Baruipur* area and it can be dated on 10th century A.D, now preserved in Directorate of Archaeology and Museum Government of West Bengal. The god is standing in the *Pratyālīdha* posture on a mule. Her right hand has been situated on the head of being and left leg rest on the waist of the animal. The left hand of the goddess bears *kartarī* and the right hand holds *Vajra*. She adorned by several types of ornaments like *kantha-hāra*, *sarpa-nupura*, *udara-bandha*, *sarpa-valaya*, *sarpa-angadas* and *karna-kundala*. The execution of the mule, with beaded string on the neck is evenly excellent. The animal is standing on an oval shaped pedestal which is decorated by the pericarp of a lotus with double queue of petals.

Originally a primitive protector of children, *Hārīti* was admitted into the Buddhist pantheon and her worship become popular even among the *Hinayanaists*. According to the Buddhist legends she was the guardian deity of *Magadha* who was in the habit of stealing and devouring young children. But this aspect was converted into the protectress deity of children under Buddha's influence. She is easily

recognised in sculptures by her association with children. She is also some times reported as holding a pomegranate which Buddha gave her as a food a substitute of human flesh. A *Hārīti* image has been recovered from Nalgora⁷⁰ (c.10th century A.D) where the goddess is seated on a two tiered lotus like pedestal in *ardhaparyankasanaposture*. She holds a baby in her left hand and her right hands a pomegranate respectively. The deity is seated under a pomegranate tree. *Pānchikā* the consort of *Haritiis* seated on the left side of the deity.

CONCLUSION

Historical evidences have revealed development and enlargement of Buddhist sites, uninterrupted temporal continuity of Buddhism on in the mentioned area of coastal Bengal in the period between 5th century but especially between 7th century and 12th century A.D. The *Vajrayāna* form of Buddhism, introduced a number of Buddha, Bodhisattvas, gods and goddesses. Some magnificent sculptural evidences have been discovered from several area of coastal West Bengal. A remarkable number of early medieval icons have been found from places still unmarked in the archaeological maps of West Bengal. A considerable number of images have been rescued from Sundarbans. The sculptures recovered from several vicinity of the coastal Bengal are not only significant from the artistic value, but are evidences conducive to reconstruction of the depiction of the socio-cultural and religious history of particular area as well as Eastern India also. This material evidences helps us to understand trade relation and cultural relation with aboard countries especially South and South-East Asian country.

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